

Portulacaria pygmaea

Pygmy porkbush

© N. Helme

Group: Eudicot

Size: 10 cm

Distribution:

Portulacaria pygmaea is restricted to the arid Richtersveld region of the Northern Cape, occurring along the lower Orange River Valley.

Importance:

This species is listed as Critically Endangered on the SANBI Red List. It has lost most of its habitat to mining and is being poached heavily and needs critical conservation intervention. It is a relative of *Portulacaria afra* (spekboom) which has important ecological and economic value. *P. pygmaea* is a Richtersveld endemic with a complete absence of cytogenetic or genomic data, making it a highly valuable candidate for foundational genetic, ecological, and conservation research into southern-African biodiversity.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 33.45 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 13.19 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.84 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.5% [Single: 7.3%, Duplicated: 92.2%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 11 377.66 kilobases

Contig number: 810

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